

EXPLAINING THE PRESENCE OR ABSENCE OF SYNTACTIC ELEMENTS IN TEACHING GRAMMAR

Zarlikov I., Seytjanov J.
Karakalpak State University

Where a statement of intention involves two separate activities, it is acceptable for speakers of American English to use *to go plus bare infinitive*. Speakers of British English would instead use *to go and plus bare infinitive*: thus where a speaker of American English might say "*I'll go take a bath*", British English speakers would say "*I'll go and have a bath*". (Both can also use the form "*to go to*" instead to suggest that the action may fail, as in "*He went to take/have a bath, but the bath was full of children.*") Similarly, *to come plus bare infinitive* is acceptable to speakers of American English, where speakers of British English would instead use *to come and plus bare infinitive*: thus where a speaker of American English might say *Come see what I bought*, British English speakers would say, *Come and see what I've bought* (notice the addition of "*have*": a common British preference).

Use of prepositions before days denoted by a single word. Where British people would say "*She resigned on Thursday*", Americans often say "*She resigned Thursday*", but both forms are common in American usage. Occasionally, the preposition is also absent when referring to months: "*I'll be here December*" (although this usage is generally limited to colloquial speech).

In the UK, *from* is used with single dates and times more often than in the United States.

Where British speakers and writers may say "*the new museum will be open from Tuesday*," Americans always say "*the new museum will be open starting Tuesday*." (This difference does not apply to phrases of the pattern *from A to B*, which are used in both British and American English.) A variation or alternative of this is the mostly American "*the play opens Tuesday*" and the mostly British "*the play opens on Tuesday*".

American English uses intransitively the verb *meet* followed by *with* to mean "*to have a meeting with*", as for business purposes ("*Yesterday we met with the CEO*"), and reserves transitive *meet* for the meanings "*to be introduced to*" ("*I want you to meet the CEO, she's such a fine lady*"), "*to come together with (someone, somewhere)*" ("*Meet the CEO at the train station*"), and "*to have a casual encounter with*" ("*Meet me in the morning*"). British English uses transitive *meet* also to mean "*to have a meeting with*"; the construction *meet with*, which actually dates back to Middle English, appears to be coming back into use in Britain, despite some commentators who preferred to avoid confusion with *meet with* meaning "*receive, undergo*" ("*the proposal was met with disapproval*"). The construction *meet up with* (as in "*to meet up with someone*"), which originated in the U.S., has long been standard in both dialects.

The verb *visit* is often used intransitively in American English, with possibly the additional meaning of "*to have a conversation*" (as in "*to visit with a friend*," a

construction that often sounds strange to British ears).

In British English, the indirect object of the verb "to write" usually requires the preposition "to", e.g. "I'll write to my MP" or "I'll write to her" (although it is not required in some situations, for example when an indirect object pronoun comes before a direct object noun, e.g. "I'll write her a letter"). In American English, the "to" can be omitted in many circumstances, e.g. "I'll write my congressman" or "I'll write him".

Some verbs that are intransitive in British English are transitive in American English; for example, British: "The workers protested against the decision." American: "The workers protested the decision." British: "To cater for a banquet." American: "To cater a banquet." British: "To claim for benefits." American (and also British): "To claim benefits."

The verb prevent can be found in two different constructions: "prevent someone from doing something"; "prevent someone doing something." The latter is well established in British English, but not in American English.

Some verbs can take either a to-infinitive construction or a gerund construction; for example, *to start/begin/omit to do something/doing something*. American English uses the gerund more often than British English.

A few 'institutional' nouns take no definite article when a certain role is implied: for example, "at sea" (as a sailor), "in prison" (as a convict), and "at/in college" (for students). Among this group, British English has "in hospital" (as a patient) and "at university" (as a student), where American English requires *in the hospital* and *at the university*. (When the implied roles of patient or student do not apply, the definite article is used in both dialects.)

American English distinguishes in back of [behind] from in the back of, the former is unknown in the UK and liable to misinterpretation as the latter. Both however distinguish in front of from in the front of

The use of the function word out as a preposition to denote an outward movement, as in "out the door" and "out the window", is standard in American English, but not quite in British writing, where out of is generally the preferred choice, although the "American" usage, usually considered regional or dialectal by British dictionaries, is gaining ground in UK speech.

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